

**THE LINGUOCULTUROLOGICAL ASPECTS OF ENGLISH, GERMAN
AND UZBEK PROVERBS ON THE TOPIC “GOODNESS” AND “EVIL”
IN THEIR ETIMOLOGICAL ANALYSES**

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ANNOTATION

In this article the proverbs of three compared languages on the topic “Goodness” and “Evil” are analysed in a semantic and linguoculturological aspect and shows the differences of culture among languages using paremiology as the object of the analysis.

***Key words:** proverbs, paremiology, linguoculturology, phraseological unit, practicality, analysis*

В статье проводится сравнительный анализ на 3 языках пословиц на тему «Добро» и «Зло» в семантическом и лингвокультурологическом аспекте, в котором приводится различие межязыковой культуры на примере паремии.

***Ключевые слова:** пословицы, паремиология, лингвокультурология, фразеологическая единица, практичность, анализы.*

INTRODUCTION

Proverbs are considered one of the most important genres of folk oral literature in world linguistics, and new aspects of the field are being revealed through in-depth study of this genre, which plays an important role in the cultural life of peoples, in comparative linguistics. Proverbs, as a genre of folk oral literature that reflects the spirituality and traditions of the people, have been passed down from generation to generation for centuries. There is no nation in the world that does not have proverbs, sayings, tales, or riddles. Therefore, any genre in folk oral literature is a cross-linguistic genre. Proverbs, which combine the features of antiquity and popularity, reflect the worldview of the people, their attitude to society, and their moral norms.

The development of paremiology in world linguistics is one of the main factors ensuring the commonality of language and culture. Each nation leaves its life experiences to generations in the form of proverbs. For this reason, in the languages of different nations, there are many proverbs that are close to each other in content and form and are harmonious. The proof of our above idea can be seen in the research carried out by Russian linguists in the fields of semantics, stylistics and pragmatics of folk proverbs. Comparative analysis of proverbs of different nations by world paremiologists, identifying commonalities and differences between them, helps to identify similarities and differences between languages and cultures.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Another universal characteristic of the paremiological layer of language is that it has the ability to store information of great cultural significance and reflect socio-cultural events.

Premias constitute a unique lexical layer in the language system. They distinguish traditions that are characteristic of the language community and culture, reflecting national-cultural, mental and social characteristics.

Premias are manifested in the process of generating information about objects and their properties, in which this information can include information about the state of realities in the world surrounding a person, as well as information about the world in the person's imagination and the possible state of affairs in it. This information expresses what a person knows, guesses, thinks, imagines about objects in the world.

If etymological analysis is carried out within the framework of comparative-historical linguistics, the main attention is paid to the search for roots in other languages, language groups and families, and the analysis of phonetic laws that have occurred, while its semantic similarity is indicated as a condition confirming the judgment. The history and etymology of each individual paremiological unit are

not based on universal schemes of motivation of word combinations, but on the semantic coherence of the components that make up the paremiological unit and the degree of desemantization of the words in the word combination.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Based on the above definitions and classifications, it is appropriate to divide proverbs in English, German and Uzbek into three main historical periods:

1. The first period is considered the Ancient period, and in English and German folklore we can see that the medieval monastic and cathedral schools had a constant influence on the cultivation of proverbs of these peoples. In the humanistic period, the explanation and memorization of philosophical words was still part of the school curriculum. Uzbek folk proverbs during this period find their interpretation mainly in the works of Yusuf Khos Hajib, Mahmud Kashgari, Ahmad Yassavi, Alisher Navoi, Lutfi, Babur Rabguzi, Abdulghazi Bahodirkhan, Ogahiy, Furqat, Nodira, Munis.

2. The second period is the medieval period of proverbs, when we can find Old High English and German proverbs of the 10th century as a result of popular sayings in the writings of the monk-teacher Notker Labeo around the year 1000. 800 proverbs collected from ancient writers are included. In the 16th century, during the first comprehensive reform, it was A. Gricola who left 88,300 common proverbs with their interpretations to posterity in 1529. “Der Deutschen Weißheit”, a collection in three parts, appeared in the 17th century (1605). The arrangement according to the first letter is alphabetical, which is why it is confusing. Schottel in his (1663) book “German-Basic Language” gives 1,230 proverbs, in addition to idioms. John Me Sailer, “Wisdom in the Street” (1810), this collection contains 4000 common English, German and Swiss proverbs considered from a religious and moral point of view. [Seiler. Fr., Deutsche Sprichwörterkunde . Mnchen 1922. – B:15] The work of organizing Uzbek folk proverbs into collections and creating special collections from them began in the second half of the 19th century.

Collections of proverbs of various nature and sizes created by folklorists, scientists and cultural workers such as N. Ostroumov (1895), B. Rahmonov, (1924), H. Zaripov (1939,1947), T. Mirzaev, A. Musoqulov (1989), B. Sarimsakov were published.

3. The third period is the current new period, during which scientists such as O. Yusupov, Sh. Rahmatullayev, T. Mirzayev, B. Sarimsakov, T. Ma'rufov, Kh. Berdiyurov, R. Rasulov, Yu. N. Ismoilov, G8. Salomov, Z. Sodikov, O. Safarov, B. Parpiboyev made a significant contribution to the development of Uzbek folk proverbs with their works. Among the English and German scientists, DR. A. E. Graf, W. von Humboldt, Duden, G. Schrader, S. Singer, Vorgang Fleischer, E. V. Rosenga, J. Reichshlein, Fr. Saylers, A. Schirmer and a number of other researchers conducted their research on the linguistic and cultural characteristics of proverbs.

Thus, the scientific views on the role of paremiology in linguistics and the close connection of this field with other fields have been widely analyzed by a number of scholars in world linguistics. In our country, proverbs, which are one of the main examples of folk oral literature, are also considered an object of research with various purposes and methods, and scientific research carried out with their help is one of the important factors in the further development of national and interethnic culture.

CONCLUSION

In the process of studying the semantic features of English, German and Uzbek proverbs expressing the theme of good and evil based on linguo-cultural analysis, the following similarities and differences between proverbs on some topics were identified:

1. Most proverbs on the theme of good and evil in English and Uzbek have almost the same meaning and content. Only words that correspond exactly to each other are not used in all three languages. Usually, proverbs with different meanings

in translation are observed to have the same meaning during a deep semantic analysis.

2. In the proverbs of the Uzbek people, hard work is mainly expressed in the image of an ant, while in the English and German people, proverbs with this content are mainly expressed in the image of domestic animals. The themes of patriotism and friendship are considered the main themes in the analyzed proverbs in the three languages.

3. Proverbs are considered to be interlingual genres of folk oral creativity that reflect folk culture, and when they are analyzed linguo-culturally, their similarities and differences in English, German and Uzbek languages were identified in the results.

4. Human qualities such as kindness, patience, responsibility, and harmony are glorified in the proverbs of the three languages, and negative qualities such as haste, malicious intent, and lying are condemned. The presence of toponyms in the proverbs and their ability to express their content are also observed in the proverbs in the three languages.

5. The classification of lexemes - linguo-culturemas - representing national costumes, national dishes, and national customs in the proverbs, carried out in each language scale, allows us to show the diversity of interethnic culture.

6. To understand the essence of some proverbs in languages, it is necessary to have knowledge of the history of the people, past experiences. In the linguo-cultural analysis of proverbs, we classified the number of proverbs according to the concepts for which we conducted the analysis as follows. (See Appendix 4.)

In the literature used as the main source, the variants of some proverbs do not exactly coincide with each other. Therefore, by deeply studying the semantic aspects of proverbs and analyzing them semantically, we can correctly select equivalents in English, German and Uzbek.

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